

Acceleration of object recognition algorithm on embedded platform

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Abstract— This paper deals with the new trend of algorithm development in embedded systems, more specifically, object localization and classification algorithms.

Different one-stage and two-stage detection algorithms are presented, which have different characteristics. The most relevant algorithm on which the article will focus is YOLO. The YOLOv3, YOLOv4 and YOLO Fastest versions are studied, as well as different acceleration libraries such as PyArmNN and NN-Pack. The embedded platform on which we work is the Raspberry Pi 4, performing performance and accuracy tests with different library and hardware configurations.

Keywords— Embedded systems, deep learning, object recognition, acceleration, optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE modern systems are becoming more and more efficient and powerful, which is making it possible to implement algorithms capable of performing tasks and solving problems that were unthinkable a few decades ago.

Object recognition is one such complex task to implement. It takes a lot of computing power and time to develop systems capable of recognizing objects accurately, as humans do. Typically, large computing centers or large teams are used to train these intelligent systems. However, the training is one thing and the subsequent use is a different matter. The resources required to operate these systems once they have learned to recognize complex patterns is much less. For that reason, the question arises whether it is possible to implement complex and accurate detection systems in resource-limited embedded devices.

The advantages of using embedded devices are mainly their low power consumption, portability and independence from any external system. On the other hand, the main disadvantage is that the power they are capable of developing is quite limited compared to other systems.

Another option, if it is desired to maintain the low power consumption and portability capabilities, without giving up power, would be to use the embedded board as the final node. This node would communicate with a remote central node that would act as a data processing system. This would require a good internet connection. In addition, the system would be completely dependent on communication latency.

The main motivation in the field of object recognition has been to successfully solve the task of autonomous driving. In order to be able to solve this type of problem, it is necessary to have very small latency and response times. For this reason, in these cases it is not feasible to set up systems that depend on the outside to make decisions. It may be possible if the speed of communications is improved in the future with technologies such as 5G. However, with the current state of the art, many tasks depend on local systems in order to function.

The main objective of the project is to implement one or more object detection algorithms using an embedded board. It is not intended to carry out a proprietary development but to experiment with existing tools to optimize and accelerate the operation of the system so that object recognition can be carried out in real time. Therefore, the detection speed has to be high enough to be seen smoothly.

Modern detection algorithms have undergone a number of notable improvements in recent years, such as greater variation among the classes that can be detected, better response to occlusions and noise in the environment, and improved handling of large-scale data. While the more traditional detection algorithms have rather limited intelligent behavior, such as the Viola-Jones[1], HOG[2] and Deformable Part-Based Model (DPM)[3], the most innovative algorithms use deep learning technology, mainly convolutional neural networks.

Object detection algorithms can be separated into one-stage and two-stage detectors. Two-stage detectors require image pre-processing to select points or regions of interest. On the other hand, single-stage detectors operate directly on the entire image.

Because of these characteristics, two-stage detectors generally have a higher level of accuracy, but they also take longer to make predictions. In contrast, single-stage detectors are faster but have more difficulty detecting small objects and suffer a decrease in accuracy. For this reason, depending on the task to be performed, one type of detector or another is more suitable. However, it should be noted that single-stage detectors have improved their accuracy values and are currently the most popular.

One of the main exponents within the two-stage detectors is Faster R-CNN[4] developed in 2015. Faster R-CNN is the R-CNN evolution[5] developed in 2013. Faster R-CNN improved the R-CNN detection time from 49 seconds to 0.2 seconds. Among the

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single-stage detectors, the most interesting are YOLO[6], SqueezeDet[7] and CornerNet[8]. YOLO was developed in 2015 and since then it has undergone several improvements reflected in its different official versions. Its strong point is that it is able to analyze images at high speed, up to 155 according to the author’s original work.

On the other hand, SqueezeDet was developed in 2016, it is quite fast, accurate and its power consumption is very low.

Finally, CornerNet is an algorithm developed in 2018. Its main difference with the other algorithms is that it represents the data differently. Instead of using a detection box, it uses only two points, the center point of the object and a corner. These features allow CornetNet to achieve very high accuracy values but with limited performance in real-time applications.

S.No	Architecture	mAP (MS-COCO)	mAP (Pascal-Voc 2007)	FPS
1	RCNN [17]	-	66%	0.1
2	SPPNet [32]	-	63.10%	1
3	Fast RCNN [33]	35.90%	70.00%	0.5
4	Faster RCNN [2]	36.20%	73.20%	6
5	Mask RCNN [44]	-	78.20%	5
6	YOLO [40]	-	63.40%	45
7	SSD [41]	31.20%	76.80%	8
8	YOLOv2 [42]	21.60%	78.60%	67
9	YOLOv3 [43]	33.00%	-	35
10	SqueezeDet [45]	-	-	57.2
11	SqueezeDet+ [45]	-	-	32.1
12	CornerNet [48]	69.2	-	4

Fig. 1: Comparative table of the main detection algorithms. Source[9]

The main characteristics of the most widespread embedded boards and platforms have been compiled. Taking into account the information shown in Figure 2, it was decided to take the Raspberry Pi 4 board as the basis of the project due to its low price and versatility.

II. YOLO ALGORITHM

YOLO[6] is one of the most popular detection algorithms today. It was initially developed by author R. Joseph in 2015. The algorithm has received 3 updates since then. Its operation, without going into much detail, is based on the use of a convolutional neural network to analyze the input images. The YOLO network separates the image into regions, analyzes these regions and provides bounding boxes and probabilities of belonging to a certain class.

This algorithm can be used in a large number of different applications due to its versatility. This is because it can be retrained to obtain a more specialized network. YOLO detects up to 80 different classes of objects and animals, so it can be considered to have learned to recognize a huge number of visual patterns.

It is worth noting that within the YOLO environment there are reduced versions of the main models called Tiny versions. These versions are characterized by being several times faster and lighter than

Tabla I: Main features of the development platforms.

Platform	Features
GPU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good at training tasks. - Use of specialized libraries such as CUDA or OpenCL. - Consumption, performance and high price.
Raspberry Pi 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low cost, around 60 USD. - High flexibility and low consumption. - Various memory configurations and great connectivity. - Very limited performance.
Nvidia Jetson Family	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hardware for deep learning and use of the Jetpack library. - Price between 130 and 600 USD. - High performance and extremely efficient.
ZYNQ Board	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hardware capable of being programmed specifically for a particular task. - Extremely versatile and efficient. - Prices between 150 and 300 USD. - Relatively limited performance.

the original algorithms. However, these Tiny models achieve lower accuracy values.

Of all the YOLO versions, the most interesting is YOLOv4[10]. This algorithm was implemented by author Alexey Bochkovskiy, among others. YOLOv4 is a great improvement in accuracy over its predecessor, achieving up to 43.5% accuracy and 65 FPS on the MS data set COCO[11].

The detector architecture is divided into four independent structural parts which will be briefly explained below.

The first component is the input layer which receives and distributes the input data to the following layers.

Fig. 2: YOLOv4 structure. Source[10]

The next part of the algorithm, called 'Backbone' in the diagram in Figure 2, is an intermediate stage formed by layers where the process of feature extraction from the input image is carried out. There are different algorithms such as ResNet, DenseNet and VGG capable of performing this task. However, YOLOv4 implements CSPDarknet53.

The next layer structure, marked as 'Neck' in Figure 2, has the function of obtaining feature maps from the output data provided by the previous layers.

YOLOv3 used 'Feature Pyramid Network' (FPN)[12] to obtain the features at different scales, thus resolving the scale dependence of the objects. YOLOv4, on the other hand, uses the algorithms 'Spatial Pyramid Pooling' (SPP)[13] y 'Path Aggregation Network (PAN)')[14]. SPP layers are responsible for solving the scaling problem by using fixed-length sequences regardless of the size of the region of interest being analyzed. On the other hand, PAN is an algorithm specialized in improving the results of the segmentation process with respect to previous versions of YOLO.

Finally, the core of the algorithm is the same as that of YOLOv3. It is the part of the network in charge of performing the detection and final localization. Different scale sizes are used to detect different object sizes.

The developers of the algorithm make use of two types of methods to improve the accuracy of the algorithm. All of them are shown in Table II.

On the one hand, the 'Bag of freebies' or BoF strategy is applied, which consists of applying the improvements to the training phase. By altering the training strategy, an improvement in accuracy can be achieved without having an impact on the inference cost. A clear example of BoF strategy would be the increase of training data.

On the other hand, the 'Bag of specials' or BoS strategy consists of implementing improvements and complements after training. In this way, the computational cost is slightly affected but a significant improvement in detection accuracy is obtained. An example would be the SPP layers involved in the YOLOv4 structure.

Tabla II: YOLOv4 improvements table.

	BackBone	Detector
BoF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CutMix - Mosaic data augmentation - DropBlock - Class label smoothing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CloU-loss - Cross mini-Batch Normalization - DropBlock - Mosaic data augmentation - Self-Adversarial Training - Multiple anchors for a single ground truth - Cosine annealing scheduler - Optimal hyperparameters - Random training shapes
BoS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mish activation - CSP - MiWRC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mish activation - SPP-block - SAM-block - PAN path-aggregation block - DioU-NMS

III. ALTERNATIVES ANALYZED

The acceleration options that have been studied to be applied on the YOLO algorithm and the Raspberry Pi 4 are: YOLOv4, PyArmNN, NNPack, YOLO Fastest and YOLOv4+TPU Coral.

Using the architecture of the YOLOv4 network explained above, the author Hyeonki Hong[?] has developed an API where the advances of the YOLOv4 network are implemented in a library written in Python language. The library is based on TensorFlow 2.0 and OpenCV. It makes use of TensorFlow Lite's own tools to convert the model from Darknet to TensorFlow Lite.

This YOLOv4 library has support for adding external accelerators, more specifically, the Google TPU Coral. Coral only works with integer values. Therefore, it is necessary that the model is subjected to a quantization process. This reduces the size of the weights from 32-bit precision floating point values to 8-bit integer values. The resulting model is 4 times smaller than the original but the impact on accuracy is minimal.

The library itself has specific options to carry out the model fitting. It is also possible to evaluate the accuracy of the models created since support is provided to generate predictions on a set of data that can be subsequently analyzed.

Another acceleration option, without using external devices, is to make use of the PyArmNN library. PyArmNN is a Python library based on ArmNN, which is an engine optimized for the ARM microprocessor architecture. ArmNN is specialized for machine learning tasks. It provides a bridge between the current neural network paradigm and low-power Cortex-A CPUs, Arm Mali GPUs and Arm Ethos NPU's. The latest version supports models created with TensorFlow Lite and ONNX. ArmNN builds from scratch the model starting from the original by replacing the original operations with equivalent ones specially designed for the hardware on which it wants to run.

NNPack is a tool developed by the author Marat Dukhan[15] that allows accelerating the calculations carried out by neural networks. Its main features include its great capacity to optimize multitasking calculations and the implementation of multiple algorithms for complex mathematical operations, such as convolution. NNPack is based on Darknet and developed in C++, which allows taking advantage of the compilation process to activate the Raspberry Pi 4 board's own hardware, such as NEON SIMD and VFPv4. Both are systems for the acceleration of certain specific tasks. So far neither NEON nor VFPv4 have been exploited by the YOLO algorithm. Thanks to the environment on which NNPack is developed, it is possible to use these extra acceleration options specific to the Raspberry Pi 4 platform.

YOLO Fastest[16] is not strictly speaking a library, it is an optimized version of the YOLO algorithm. Its weights have been reduced as much as possible by optimization techniques such as pruning and clustering. It could be said that this line of optimization does not focus on trying to optimize the system around the

model but the model itself. Like the NNpack package, its development is based on Darknet and in fact, they have great similarities with each other. While the YOLOv4 model has a size of 250 megabytes, YOLO Fastest occupies only 1.32 megabytes. This allows it to be, in priority, the most agile algorithm of all those seen so far.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

Two different platforms have been used to perform the experiments. The first, a laptop computer that serves as a control platform with which to compare the results of the second platform, the Raspberry Pi 4.

The first device features an Intel i7 4510U CPU with 64-bit x86 architecture and 22 nanometer technology. It has 2 physical cores and 4 processing threads capable of running at 3.10 GHz as turbo frequency and 2 GHz as base frequency. The cache memory is distributed with 4 MB in the L3, 512 KB in the L2 and 128 KB of L1 and its TDP or 'Thermal Design Power' is 15 watts. Along with this central computing unit, 8 GB of DDR3 RAM memory is mounted and the operating system is Ubuntu in its version 18.04.5 LST 64 bits.

On the other hand, the Raspberry Pi 4 model B features an ARMv8-A CPU with 64-bit ARM architecture. The chip is designed with up to 16 nanometer technology in some components, but is usually 28 nanometers. The cache memory is 1 MB in size in its L2 layer and 32 + 48 KB per core in the L1 cache. The ARMv8-A chip has 4 cores running at a frequency of 1.5 GHz with a power consumption between 3 and 7 watts depending on the workload.

The base frequency can be increased up to 2 GHz by changing some parameters in the boot file of the board. At an advanced stage of experimentation, this configuration is carried out to further optimize performance.

The board model used has 2 GB of LPDDR4 RAM and its operating system is Debian version 10.9 32-bit.

The parameters that have been used to compare the experimental results are precision and performance.

The former is expressed with the metric mAP or 'mean average precision'. mAP is a very extended metric and makes use of a tool called 'Intersection over Union'. IoU is used to evaluate the mean average precision of a class, by means of the differences in areas between the expected and result detection boxes. The dataset used to measure the accuracy of the models is the 2017 validation set of COCO[11].

Performance is expressed in 'frames per second' or FPS. The FPS measure defines the number of frames that are analyzed each second in a video sequence.

The YOLOv4 library alternative is the one that

has achieved the best results. Thanks to the use of the external accelerator TPU Coral, 25 FPS can be achieved without major performance losses. However, we have experimented with a large number of models generated from this library before achieving these results. All possible types of quantization have been tested to study the impact that this transformation can have on the resulting models.

In Figures 3 and 4, the results of applying quantization on the performance on the Intel platform and Raspberry, respectively, can be observed. Figure 5, on the other hand, shows the accuracy results of these same models.

Fig. 3: Performance of models optimized with TensorFlow Lite on x86 platform.

The most notable differences are observed between the YOLOv4 Tiny and YOLOv4 models. However, a substantial difference can also be seen between the models using a 640x480 detection window size and the rest, which are configured with a 320x320 size. The latter, having a smaller pixel load to work with, are able to provide higher performance. As far as the quantized models are concerned, no major performance differences have been observed between them except for the quantized model with 8-bit precision integers. The Intel processor does not seem to behave well working with this type of data.

Fig. 4: Performance of models optimized with TensorFlow Lite on ARM platform.

When studying the results in Figure 4 obtained on the Raspberry, it can be seen that the YOLOv4 models offer performance that barely reaches 0.2 FPS.

While the Tiny YOLOv4 models are close to 3 FPS. The quantized model with 16-bit floating point values shows negative performance values because it did not run on this platform.

Fig. 5: Optimized model accuracy with TensorFlow Lite.

The accuracy values shown in Figure 5 show that the main impact on the accuracy of the models is caused by the reduction of the detection window size. The accuracy of the optimized models is between 22 and 30 percent.

We have tried to use the PyArmNN library to speed up the performance of the Raspberry Pi as it is compatible with previously seen Tensorflow Lite models. In this way, it was intended to run YOLOv4 models with the PyArmNN library.

However, the results were not satisfactory due to incompatibilities between the network structure and the library itself.

The NNPack library was successfully implemented using the YOLOv3 architecture. The YOLOv4 network seen so far does not have an architecture compatible with this library. However, the performance achieved was around 0.5 FPS, which is a lower result than that achieved with the YOLOv4 library. For this reason, it cannot be considered a good solution to perform acceleration. The NNPack library includes support for enabling the NEON and VFPv4 coprocessors. However, in this case it barely brought an improvement of 0.1 FPS. To be more precise, with the default configuration 0.3 FPS was achieved, adding the NNPack library increased it to 0.4 and finally, by activating the coprocessors the final 0.5 FPS was reached.

The last optimization line that was analyzed is the YOLO Fastest model. 2.5 FPS performance was obtained when running with the default values. However, relying on the implementation seen with NN-Pack, it is possible to enable the NEON and VFPv4 coprocessors increasing the performance up to 3.5 FPS. If the base frequency is increased to the Raspberry from 1.5 GHz to 2.2, the final result of this optimization line improved to 4.6 FPS. This is the best result ever achieved without using any external

acceleration device.

Finally, a version of Tiny YOLOv4 was generated and configured to run using the Coral device as an external accelerator. For the model to work, it was necessary to convert the instructions so that the accelerator could interpret them. The model needs to be quantized with integer values and 8-bit precision. In addition, the network activation functions had to be defined as reLU type to be compatible with the Coral TPU instructions.

The results obtained depended on the input video resolution, but hovered around 8 FPS for heavy 1080p videos and up to 25 with lighter 360p videos. In any case, the results were considerably better after installing the external accelerator.

The results of the experimentation are compiled below. The performance and accuracy values for each implementation carried out can be observed.

Tabla III: Results acceleration on Raspberry Pi 4.

Implementation	Performance (FPS Max.)	Accuracy(%)
YOLOv4 640x480	0.25	60.1
Tiny YOLOv4 640x480	2.5	28.7
Tiny YOLOv4 TFLite 320x320	2.6	22.2
PyArmNN+YOLOv4	-	-
NNPack+YOLOv3	0.5	33.1
YOLO Fastest	2.5	24.4
Yolo Fastest+Neon+VFPv4	3.5	24.4
Yolo Fastest+Neon+VFPv4+2.2GHz	4.6	24.4
Tiny YOLOv4 TPU CORAL	25	29.2

Figure 6 shows the final result of the acceleration using the Coral installation. The performance that can be seen is lower than that reported in the results because these have always been expressed in terms of maximum FPS. In addition, in order to capture the information, the Raspberry's frequency had to be reduced from 2.2Ghz to 2 to prevent the board from failing.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, to implement a real-time object recognition algorithm on an embedded board, it is necessary to have an algorithm that is as optimal and fast as possible. This is because the detection task is very computationally demanding.

Acceptable results have been seen using highly optimized models such as YOLO Fastest, using Rasp-

Fig. 6: YOLOv4 running with Coral TPU at 360p resolution. [Link to video.](#)

berry’s own coprocessors and increasing the base frequency of the Raspberry.

However, for the recognition task to run smoothly, it is highly recommended to pair the system with an external accelerator such as the Coral TPU. With a combined cost around 120 USD, they come to offer superior performance to the platform with x86 architecture that usually costs several times more.

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